

OVERVIEW OF TOOLS USED IN SOFTWARE AND SYSTEMS LIFE CYCLE AUTOMATION

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Abstract

The article describes tools for automating the life cycle of software and systems - the Telelogic family of integrated products. The use of such tools can significantly reduce the duration and cost of developing systems and software while simultaneously improving the quality of the development process and, as a consequence, the quality of the developed software.

Keywords: software, life cycle, standards, Telelogic, Telelogic DOORS, Telelogic TAU, Telelogic SYNERGY, Telelogic DocExpress.

The large size and high complexity of software development, constrained by project budget and time constraints, can lead to low quality end software products and the system as a whole. In this regard, more attention has recently been paid to modern technologies and tools (CASE tools) that provide automation of software life cycle processes. The use of such tools can significantly reduce the time and cost of developing

systems and software, while improving the quality of the development process and the quality of the resulting software. Modern tools that effectively support software and systems lifecycle processes include Telelogic's family of integrated products. The main tools of this family are: [1]

The Telelogic DOORS tool can be used in the ordering, delivery, and development processes (

Table 1).

Table 1.

**Activities and tasks of the order,
delivery and development processes supported by the Telelogic DOORS tool.**

The name of the process	Job title	Supported task content	Table number
Order	Preparing the order process	Description of concept or ordering need. System requirements analysis. Software requirements analysis.	1
Supply	To plan	Analysis of order requirements	2
Projecting	System requirements analysis	Analysis of the scope of application of the system and determination of requirements for it	4
	System architecture design	Allocation of system requirements between hardware and software architecture objects and manual operations and further clarification of requirements	5
	Software requirements analysis	Defining software requirements	6
	Software architecture design	Distribution of requirements for a software object among its components and further clarification of requirements	7
	Software engineering	Distribution of technical requirements for components among software modules and further clarification of requirements	8

In this table, the numbers of tasks and tasks of the software life cycle are given according to their hierarchical numbers in the ISO/IEC 12207:1995 standard and its original analogues ISO / IEC 12207–2003 and ISO / IEC 12207–99 [2].

Telelogic TAU family of tools. The Telelogic TAU family of tools is designed to automate the work and tasks of the software and systems development process. This family provides a visual development environment based on the use of the UML universal modeling language, with the ability for software to automatically generate code afterwards. The use of the Telelogic TAU family allows to combine the language of communication between system analysts, designers,

programmers and other developers, to accelerate and improve the quality of software and system design, to automate the testing of software modules, components, software and software [3].

The Telelogic TAU family includes the following tools:

- TAU/Model Author – a tool for drawing model diagrams;
- TAU/Architect – a tool for system engineers;
- TAU/Developer – a tool for software developers;
- TAU/Tester – a tool for testers.

Telelogic SYNERGY. The tool is designed to automate software changes and configuration management. Telelogic SYNERGY supports changes

to the output of development or maintenance processes, automates the configuration management process of software and systems life cycle [4].

Telelogic DocExpress. The tool is designed to support the software lifecycle documentation process. Telelogic DocExpress allows you to automate the reception of source data for documentation from various sources, keep source data and documents up-to-date, automatically format documents according to current documentation standards, and simplify document storage.

Telelogic TAU Logiscope. The tool family is part of the Telelogic TAU family and can be used by quality engineers and testers. Designed to support lifecycle tasks related to testing reviews, evaluations, and development intervals. The use of Telelogic TAU Logiscope allows you to manage the quality of processes, intermediate and final products of the software life cycle, and reduce the cost and time of projects. Telelogic TAU Logiscope allows you to automate the search for errors in the source codes of software modules, components, software objects, evaluate the quality, complexity and compliance of the source codes, evaluate the test scope of the source codes [5].

The Telelogic TAU Logiscope family includes the following instruments:

- Logiscope Audit – a tool for evaluating the quality of source software codes and graphic analysis;
- Logiscope RuleChecker – tool for checking compliance of source code with accepted rules;
- Logiscope TestChecker – a tool for checking source code coverage with test packages;
- Logiscope Reviewer is a tool that combines the capabilities of Logiscope Audit and Logiscope RuleChecker.

The Telelogic TAU Logiscope family supports supporting life cycle processes related to quality management of processes and products: quality assurance, verification, certification, joint analysis, audit [6].

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